

Main features of polysemantic words in the Uzbek and English languages

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Abstract: This article examines about main features of polysemantic words in the Uzbek and English languages. To communicate and establish relationship with other, people use language as tool of communication Human beings are free to express their ideas, it means that they have the ability to transfer ideas from one person to the others. The function of language is not only as a tool of communication but also as a tool to persuade and influence people to do something.

Key words: polysemantic, language, phenomenon, semantic, semasiology, paradigmatic, syntagmatic.

People use various of ways in creative media in order to get most effective attention from the listener or reader. Even human use different style either in social or in the politic or economic aspect. It is said that good speakers or writers will get a success on their aim depend on how well people use a word, how they talk to other, what they say to a dissatisfied person, and how well they understand what they are told to do through the meaning. To learn the system of language, we have particular study that we learned in order to understand the phenomenon the language itself. It is called linguistics.

There are so many fields that categorize every types of linguistic subject, one of them semantic. Semantic is the study of meaning that is used for understanding human expression through language.

Thus meaning is the object of semasiological study. So semasiology is concerned with the meaning of words, the change of meaning, the semantic structure of words, synonyms, homonyms and polysemy. Many words in a language is considered to have many meanings because if a person uses a separate word for each of newly emerging concepts in the daily life, the number of words will be increased and it becomes impossible to memorize the words. As a result, the language becomes difficult to use and gradually becomes unusable. Polysemantic words have emerged to create ease in language and increase its meaning. Polysemy is the capacity for a word or phrase to have multiple meanings, usually related by contiguity of meaning within a semantic field. Polysemantic words always serve to enrich the language, but at the same time these words create some confusions in the language. There is context to avoid such confusion. It is the context that clearly defines the meaning of polysemantic words in language. The true exact meaning of a word is determined

within context. Other meanings come to the fore only when the word is used in certain contexts. This is true of all polysemantic words. For example the adjective yellow, when used in isolation is understood to denote a certain colour, whereas other meanings of this word, e.g. “envious”, “suspicious”, “sensational”, “corrupt” are perceived only in certain contexts, “a yellow look”, “a yellow press”. As can be seen from the examples discussed above we understand by the term context the minimal stretch of speech determining each individual meaning of the word. This is not to imply that polysemantic words have meanings only in the context. The semantic structure of the word has an objective existence as a dialectical entity which embodies dialectical permanency and variability. The context individualises the meanings, brings them out. It is in this sense that we say that meaning is determined by context. It is common knowledge that context prevents from any misunderstanding of meanings. For instance, the adjective “dull”, if used out context, would mean different things to different people or nothing at all. It is only combination with other words that it reveals its actual meaning: “a dull pupil”, “a dull play”, “dull weather”. Sometimes, however, such a minimum context fails to reveal the meanings of word, and it may be correctly interpreted only through a second-degree context as in the following example: “The man was large, but his wife was even fatter”. The word “fatter” here serves as a kind of indicator pointing that “large” describes a stout man and not a big one.

From the discussion of the paradigmatic and syntagmatic relations it follows that a full understanding of the semantic structure of any lexical item can be gained only from the study of a variety of contexts in which the word is used, i.e. from the study of the intralinguistic relations of words in the flow of speech. This is of greatest importance in connection with the problem of the synchronic approach to polysemy. The meaning or meanings of polysemantic words observed only in certain contexts may be viewed as determined either by linguistic (or verbal) contexts or extralinguistic (non-verbal) contexts.

The two more or less universally recognized main types of linguistic contexts which serve to determine individual meanings of words are the lexical context and the grammatical context. These types are differentiated depending on whether the lexical or the grammatical aspect is predominant in determining the meaning. In lexical context of primary importance are the groups of lexical items combined with the polysemantic word under consideration. This can be illustrated by analyzing different lexical contexts in which polysemantic words are used. The adjective “heavy”, e.g., in isolation is understood as meaning of “great weight, weighty” (heavy load, heavy table). When combined with lexical group of words denoting natural

phenomena such as wind, storm, snow, etc. It means “striking, falling with force, abundant” as can be seen from the contexts, e.g. heavy rain, wind, storm. In combination with the words industry, artillery and the like, heavy has the meaning “the larger kind of something” as in heavy industry, heavy artillery. It can be easily observed that the main factor in bringing out this or that individual meaning of the words is the lexical meaning of the words with which heavy is combined. This also can be proved by the fact that when we want to describe the individual meaning of a polysemantic word, we find it sufficient to use this word in combination with some members of a certain lexical group. To describe the meanings of the word handsome, for example, it is sufficient to combine it with the following words –a) man, person, b) size, reward, sum. The meanings “good looking” and considerable, ample” are adequately illustrated by the contexts. The meanings determined by lexical contexts are sometimes referred to as lexically (or phraseologically) bound meanings which implies that such meanings are to be found only in certain lexical contexts. Some linguists go so far as to assert that word meaning in general can be analysed through its collocability with other words. They hold the view that if we know all the possible collocations into which polysemantic word can enter, it is possible to know all its meaning. In grammatical contexts it is the grammatical (mainly the syntactic) structure of the context that serves to determine various individual meanings of a polysemantic word. One of the meanings of the verb “make”, e.g. “to force to induce” is found only in the grammatical context possessing the structure to make somebody do something or in other terms this particular meaning occurs only if the verb “make” is followed by a noun and the infinitive of some other verbs (to make smb. laugh, go, work). Another meaning of this verb “to become”, “to turn out to be” is observed in the contexts of a different structure, i.e. make followed by an adjective and a noun (to make a good wife, a good teacher). Such meanings are sometimes described as grammatically (or structurally) bound meanings. Cases of the type she will make a good teacher may be referred to as syntactically bound meanings, because the syntactic function of the verb “make” in this particular context (a link verb, part of the predicate) is indicative of its meaning “to become, to turn out to be”. A different syntactic function of the verb, e.g. that of the predicate (to make machines, tables, etc.) excludes the possibility of the meaning “to become, to turn out to be “ . In a number of contexts, however, we find that both the lexical and grammatical aspects should be taken into consideration. The grammatical structure of the context although indicative of the difference between the meaning of the word in this structure and the meaning of the same word in a different grammatical structure may be insufficient to indicate in which of its individual meanings the word in question is used. If we

compare the contexts of different grammatical structures, e.g. to take+noun, and to take to+noun, we can safely assume that they represent different meanings of the verb to take, but it is only when we specify the lexical context, i.e. the lexical group with which the verb is combined in the structure to take+noun (to take coffee, tea; books, pencils; the bus, the tram) that we can say that the context determines the meaning. It is usual in modern linguistic science to use the terms pattern or structure to denote grammatical contexts. Patterns may be represented in conventional symbols, e.g. to take smth. as to take+N. to take to smb. as take to+N2. It is argued that difference in the distribution of the word is indicative of the difference in meaning. Conventional symbols habitually used in distributional patterns are as follows: N-stands for nouns or their functional equivalents, e.g. personal pronouns. V-stands for verbs except auxiliary and modal verbs. A-stands for adjectives or their functional equivalents, e.g. ordinal numbers. D-stands for adverbs or their functional equivalents, e.g. at home. Distributional pattern, however, does not imply sameness of meaning. As was shown above, the same pattern to take+Noun may represent different meanings of the verb to take dependent mainly on the lexical group of the nouns with which it is combined.

Dealing with verbal contexts it is considered to be only linguistic factors: lexical groups of words, syntactic structure of the context and so on. There are cases, however, when the meaning of the word is ultimately determined not by these linguistic factors, but by the actual speech situation in which this word is used. The meanings of the noun ring, e.g. in to give somebody a ring, or of the verb get in I have got it are determined not only by the grammatical or lexical context, but much more so by the actual speech situation. The noun “ring” in such context may possess the meaning “a circlet of precious metal” or “a call on the telephone”; the meaning of the verb “to get” in this linguistic context may be interpreted as “possess” or “understand” depending on the actual situation in which these words are used. It should be pointed out however that such cases, though possible, are not actually very numerous. The linguistic context is by far a more potent factor in determining word meaning. Attempts to study the inner structure of the vocabulary revealed that in spite of its heterogeneity the English word-stock may be analysed into numerous sub-systems the members of which have some features in common, thus distinguishing them from the members of other lexical sub-systems. Words can be classified in various ways. Here, however, it is concerned only semantic classification of words. Classification into monosemantic and polysemantic words are based on the number of meanings the word possesses. More detailed semantic classifications are generally

based on the semantic similarity (or polarity) of words or their component morphemes. The scope and the degree of similarity (polarity) may be different.

In conclusion, we analyzed pointed out that different meanings of polysemantic words “make” it possible to refer the same word to different lexico-semantic groups. Thus, make in the meaning of “construct” is naturally a member of lexico-semantic group as the verbs produce, manufacture, etc, whereas in the meaning of compel it is regarded as a member of a different lexico-semantic group made up by the verbs force, induce, etc. Lexico-semantic groups seem to play a very important role in determining individual meanings of polysemantic words in lexical contexts. Analysing lexical contexts it is seen that the verb take, e.g, in combination with any member of the lexical group denoting means of transportation is synonymous with the verb go (take the tram, the bus, etc). When combined with members of another lexical group the same verb is synonymous with to drink (to take tea, coffee, etc). Such word groups are often used not only in scientific lexicological analysis, but also in practical classroom teaching. Polysemy is very characteristic of the English vocabulary due to monosyllabic character of English words and the predominance of root words. The greater frequency of the word, the greater number of meanings that constitute its semantic structure. Frequency-combinability—polysemy are closely connected.

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